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Term paper Review on the Challenges and Prospects of Health Policy Implementation: Ethiopian Context

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1. Executive summary

Health policy is now becoming a central issue in many developing countries, as national health plans and programs are key policies for governments. It should be based on the needs of the population and should have the support of all actors. Health policy implementation can be facilitated by the development of clear guidance about expectations and the distribution of responsibilities for policy actions. In an attempt to foster the delivery of healthcare services, governments have been actively implementing healthcare policies. However, there are a number of challenges when implementing national health policies, especially in low-income countries like Ethiopia. Objective of this term paper is to assess the challenges and prospects of health policy implementation in the Ethiopian context.

It summarized that key challenges of the health policy implementation Ethiopia context involves Political instability, inadequate infrastructure and resources, inadequate funding, fragmented health system, a lack planning for policy implementation, a key human resource challenge, a lack of adequate training and staff capacity building, a lack of leadership, commitment, and ideology, lack stakeholder engagement, lack of implementation guidance and ongoing communication, lack of organizational culture, lack of accountability, lack of the monitoring and evaluation; weak inter-sectoral collaboration; inadequately managed urbanization and industrialization. However, it can summarize those prospects of the health policy implementation in the Ethiopia context along with their major activities: increased funding, strengthening of the primary healthcare system, and strengthening of partnerships; ensure community engagement and ownership; improve human resource development and management; strengthen governance and leadership; improve health infrastructure; improve traditional medicine; improving engagement of stakeholders in improving quality of care. It recommended that effective health policy implementation is critical and essential to achieving success of health policies outcome in Ethiopia. Finally, at national, regional and local levels, efforts will also be make to integrate and mainstream elements of the health policy within the policies and programs of all other sectors, fostering inter-sectoral collaboration. In require effort to understand how policy implementation occurs and how it can be improved provides suggestions for policy decision-makers at national and local levels to close the implementation gap.

Keywords: Challenge, Health policy, Prospect, Policy Implementation, Ethiopia.

2. Introduction

Health Policy is refers to the decision, plans and actions undertaken with a view of achieving a specific health care objective. Policy implementation is refers to the actions that are conducted in executing a law or directive that has been put into place. This was measured by the attainment of the policy goals, the

sustainability of the policy and the number of projects executed. Policy is what governments choose to do or not to do. It is a complex process with multiple stages and actors, and often spans years, even decades. Health policy is assumed to embrace courses of action (and inaction) that affect the set of institutions, organizations, services and funding arrangements of the health system. It includes policy made in the public sector (by government) as well as policies in the private sector.

A country in the horn of Africa region and one of the oldest states, Ethiopia has poor health outcomes even by sub-Saharan Africa's standards characterized by many decades without a national health policy, weak healthcare system infrastructure and low government spending. Crucially, Ethiopia has taken critical steps in policy and programs to improving the country's health status. Nevertheless, a World Bank study simulating different scenarios to meet the United Nations Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) on health in the country shows that unprecedented levels of aid flow would be needed. In 1993, the government published the country's first health policy in 50 years setting the vision for the healthcare sector development for the next two decades. The policy tried to reorganize the health services delivery system with the objective of contributing positively to the overall socio-economic development effort of the country. Major aspects of this policy focus on fiscal and political decentralization, expanding the primary health care system, and encouraging partnerships and the participation of nongovernmental actors.

Developing a policy is just the first step; for policies to contribute to the successful delivery of health services, they must be effectively implemented. Challenges to implementation are referred to as "implementation challenges." They can be rooted in a variety of causes, including opposition from key stakeholders, inadequate human or financial resources, lack of clarity on operational guidelines or roles and responsibilities for implementation, conflicts with other existing policies, lack of coordination and collaboration between parties responsible for implementation, or lack of motivation or political will.

Relevance to Policy implementation refers to the mechanisms, resources, and relationships that link health policies to program action. It includes both technical and relational aspects not only specifying the institutions responsible for implementation but also ensuring that the institutions have the capacity for implementation and that the relations among institutions are conducive for collaboration (Hardee et al., 2012). Understanding the nature of policy implementation is important because international experience shows that policies, once adopted, are not always implemented as envisioned and do not necessarily achieve intended results (Bhuyan et al., 2010).

To address implementation challenges, stakeholders must assess the root cause of the challenge and develop targeted strategies to address each challenge in collaboration with other interested and empowered parties. Throughout the policy development, implementation, and monitoring processes, challenges should be continually assessed and addressed. Implementation is an ongoing process of decision making by key actors who work in complex policy and institutional contexts and face pressures from interested as well as opposing parties. As such, the motivation, flow of information, and balance of power and resources among stakeholders influences policy implementation processes. Ultimately, overcoming policy implementation challenges will require commitment and perseverance by a range of stakeholders, possibly over a prolonged period (Bhuyan et al., 2010).

The ability to address policy implementation challenges is a key capability for government, policymakers, and civil society. Addressing policy challenges requires individual and institutional skills and competencies to understand the policy environment governing the health system, the configuration of the health system in the context of the government structure, and the needs of beneficiaries/clients and implementers. It requires the ability to critically assess the true root of policy implementation challenges whether it is sociological, political, structural, institutional, or cultural and to create targeted solutions to address them. Finally, it requires engendering stakeholder buy-in and commitment to take action, determining resources required for the proposed solution, implementing a solution to remove the challenges, and enacting accountability mechanisms to ensure that challenges have been addressed (Bhuyan et al., 2010; Cross et al., 2001). In this term paper will be introduced to emphasis on the challenges and prospects of the health policy implementation of the Ethiopian context.

3. Statement of the Problem

Ethiopia, home to more than 112 million people as of 2019, has passed through various political transitions that caused health policy inefficiencies, better understanding of why existing health policies are not being implemented effectively. Ethiopia has implemented the first Health Sector Transformation Plan (HSTP-I) from 2015/16 to 2019/20, during which significant achievements were registered in improving the health of our population and increasing access to and utilization of health services. Health outcome indicators have shown improvement, with a remarkable reduction in morbidity and mortality from major communicable diseases such as HIV, tuberculosis and malaria. Even though significant improvements, mortality and morbidity from communicable diseases and maternal and child health conditions are still high. The prevalence of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) and injuries are on the rise creating a triple burden of diseases for the health system. There is a high disparity in service utilization and health outcomes among people in different geographical areas and socio-economic groups. The quality of health care is still sub-optimal. The health system is also challenged by emerging pandemics such as COVID-19.

The Ethiopian health sector is well known for its strong community health program through initiatives such as the health extension program (HEP). The HEP delivers cost effective basic services to all Ethiopians, mainly women and children. HEP is underpinned by the core principle of community ownership, which empowers communities to manage health problems specific to their communities, thus enabling them to safeguard their own health. However, during the implementation of HSTP-I, the link between primary healthcare units and HEP began showing signs of slowdown. This was caused by several factors, including inadequate support from political leadership, dissatisfaction and fatigue among HEWs, sub-optimal facility readiness, and community demands that surpassed the scope of the services provided at health posts. The epidemiologic transition also posed new challenges to the health system, in particular the rise in NCD burden. Community-based activities by HEWs, including household visits, have declined in recent years. Further, the implementation of the strategy for generating grassroots community faced such challenges as low literacy, slow progress in community training (level-I training), limited supportive supervision, and lack of incentives, recognition, or appreciations of volunteers.

Ministry of Health held regular JSC meetings with RHBs, agencies, donors, developing partners to track program performance, work out technical and operational issues, and coordinate health sector's multi-sectoral, multi-level activities. However, high turnover of leadership at all levels has affected the overall implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of the health sector plan. And also, introduction of new strategies without sufficient consideration of local contexts has sometimes delayed implementation. Delays were compounded by weak institutional capacities, low ownership and governance mechanisms, and suboptimal integration of vertical and horizontal components.

To address the quality arm of the HSTP-I agenda, the National Quality Strategy (NQS) was developed. It focuses on ensuring reliable, excellent clinical care, protecting patients, staff, and attendants from harm, and improving the efficiency of the delivery of care, while increasing access, equity, and dignity of care for Ethiopians. Accordingly, a number of service and/or program specific quality improvement initiatives were developed and implemented. However, a range of problems undermined implementation, including lack of coordination at national and subnational level, weak accountability mechanisms, sub-optimal quality measurement data and tools, weak information use culture, shortage of a wide range of service inputs (including finance, competent and compassionate workforce, medical supplies and public health infrastructure). It is well known that there are a number of challenges when implementing national health policies. Evidence demonstrates that these challenges often lead policies to be enacted in such a way that they are only implemented partially or diverge from the original aims of the policy. This can result in an 'implementation gap' between the policy goals and outcomes or even lead to policy failure.

In an effort to understand how policy implementation occurs and how it can be improved, a great deal of research has studied. This evidence provides suggestions for policy decision-makers at national and local levels to close the implementation gap. Despite the increasing challenges facing the health sector in Ethiopia as well as the visible gaps in execution of the health policy, that calls for adequate health service provision

as well as universal the health policy implementation. The current term paper is seeks to examine the challenges and prospects of health policy implementation in the case of Ethiopian context.

4. Objective of Study

The general objective of the study term paper is seeks to examine the challenges and prospects of health policy implementation in the case of Ethiopian context.

5. Discussion and Analysis

The empirical data of the study will be useful to policy makers who may require information on importance, concepts and principles of health policy, and the context, content, process and actors to be considered in health policy development, implementation and analysis, challenges and prospects of the Health policy implementation in Ethiopia context. The study may also provide a sense of direction for donors and non-governmental organizations who may cooperate with the health sector towards achieving the health objective of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).

5.1. Discussion of the Health Policy Concepts, and Implementation

Health policy is now becoming a central issue in many developing countries, as national health plans and programs are key policies for governments. It should be based on the needs of the population and should have the support of all actors. Health policy is a complex issue as health is by itself unpredictable and uncertain. Government should develop a viable health policy document and devise health plans and programs to implement it. Health economists, managers, planners or policymakers need to know the importance, concepts and principles of health policy, and the context, content, process and actors to be considered in health policy development, implementation and analysis. They also need to understand the links between health policy and other social policies, such as economic policies and education policies.

Health policy is assumed to embrace courses of action (and inaction) that affect the set of institutions, organizations, services and funding arrangements of the health system. It includes policy made in the public sector (by government) as well as policies in the private sector. However, as health is influenced by many determinants outside the health system, health policy analysts are also interested in the actions and intended actions of organizations external to the health system that have an impact on health (for example, the food, education, agriculture or pharmaceutical industries). Just as there are various definitions of what policy is, so there are many ideas about its focus: an economist may say health policy is about the allocation of scarce resources for health; a planner sees it as ways to influence the determinants of health in order to improve public health; and for a doctor it is all about health services (Walt *et al*, 2008). For Walt, health policy is synonymous with politics and deals explicitly with who influences policymaking, how they exercise that influence, and under what conditions. This variety of views about focus is reflected in a variety of views about the analysis of health policy.

Devising a framework for incorporating politics into health policy needs to include consideration of the *content* of policy. Many of the previous health policies focus on a particular policy, describing what it declares to do, the strategy to achieve set goals and whether or not it has achieved them. These are the 'what' questions of health policy. But they cannot be divorced from the 'who' and 'how' questions: who makes the decisions? Who implements them? Under what conditions will they be introduced and executed, or ignored? In other words, the content is not separate from the politics of policymaking. For example, in Ethiopia, when the government saw evidence that utilization of health services had not improved as intended after the implementation of Health Sector Development Programme (HSDP) I, it introduced the HEP. To understand how the government made that decision, you need to know something about the political context (an election coming up, and the desire to win votes); the power of the prime minister or the minister of health to introduce change; and the role of evidence in influencing the decision, among other things.

Health policy is an organized set of values, principles and objectives for improving health and reducing the burden of disorders in a population. It defines a vision for the future and helps to establish a model for

action. Policy also states the level of priority that a government assigns to health in relation to other social policies. Policy is generally formulated to cover a long period, typically 5 to 10 years. Often the terms 'plans' and 'programs' are used interchangeably. They are considered complementary to policies and provide the means for implementing actions.

A **health plan** is a detailed pre-formulated scheme for implementing strategic actions that favour the promotion of health, the prevention of disorders, and treatment and rehabilitation. Such a plan allows the implementation of the vision, values, principles and objectives defined in the policy. A plan usually includes strategies, timeframes, resources required, targets to be achieved, indicators and activities. A plan can correspond to the same administrative division and period of time as the health policy. However, this does not always have to be so: a plan can be developed for a smaller administrative division or a shorter period than the policy. A **health program** is an intervention or series of interventions with a highly focused objective for the promotion of health, the prevention of disorders, and treatment and rehabilitation. A programme usually focuses on a specific health priority and, like health plans, programs must be adequately designed, budgeted for, monitored and evaluated. In contrast to the policy and plan, the program is frequently implemented in a smaller administrative division or for a shorter period.

5.1.1. Health Policy, Plan and Program Implementation

A health policy can be implemented through the priority strategies identified by the plan and the priority interventions identified by the plan/programme. The implementation of these strategies and interventions requires several actions.

Step 1: Disseminate the policy; once the health policy and plan have been formulated, it is important that the ministry of health disseminate and communicate the policy to the health district offices and other partner agencies, targeting key individuals. **Step 2: Generate political support and funding;** after a policy has been written, active stakeholder participation and communication activities should be initiated. These activities should last for a few months in order to ensure that enough political support and funding are given for implementation. It is essential to have well-connected facilitators who can advocate the policy at the highest levels of government and in key agencies. **Step 3: Develop supportive organisation;** the implementation of health policy requires a competent group of professionals with expertise in health. This group should be responsible for managing plans and programs, ensuring that the population can access health interventions of high quality, which are responsive to expressed needs. **Step 4: Set up pilot projects in demonstration areas;** it is recommended that the ministry of health establish pilot projects in demonstration areas where policy, plans and programs can be implemented more rapidly and evaluated more thoroughly than elsewhere in the country.

Step 5: Empower health providers; it is important to obtain knowledge of how providers function in the country and how they relate to each other within the health system. This knowledge makes it possible to use existing resources more efficiently and to deliver better health interventions. The characteristics of providers may have a strong influence on the way that health interventions are delivered to the population. The best providers are small multidisciplinary teams, comprising persons from different fields who combine their skills and use their collective wisdom to deal with the complexities of the population's health. **Step 6: Reinforce inter-sectorial coordination;** most of the health problems need health interventions that are delivered to populations through sectors other than the health sector. **Step 7: Promote interactions among stakeholders;** in order to ensure the delivery of health interventions that respond to the needs of a population it is necessary for multiple interactions to occur between the stakeholders. These interactions happen at different levels of the organization of a country or region.

5.2. Challenges and Prospects of the Health Policy Implementation in the Ethiopia

The sections below discuss key topics from existing challenges and Prospects of health policy implementation in the Ethiopia context;

5.2.1. Challenges of the health policy implementation in the Ethiopia Context

A lack planning for health policy Implementation: Challenges such as disagreements over budgets and uncertainty over funding delayed the development of local strategic plans. Poor planning may lead to issues such as insufficient numbers of trained staff or resources to handle the burden of managing a new policy. A lack of planning may also increase the risks of unintended consequences. In addition, the context of a local area will specifically shape how a given policy is implemented in that area this interaction will influence policy outcomes. It is self evident that one-size will not fit all.

Inadequate funding: Inadequate funding is another significant challenge in implementing health policies in Ethiopia. The government's allocation to the health sector is limited, and there is a reliance on external funding from donor countries and organizations. The government has acknowledged this issue and has taken steps to increase health financing from domestic sources. The current expenditure on health stands at around 4% of the GDP, which is lower than the 6% recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) for low-income countries (WHO, 2020). The inadequate funding has limited the ability of the government to provide necessary healthcare services.

Inadequate infrastructure and resources: The lack of infrastructure and resources, such as hospitals, medical supplies, and personnel, is another significant challenge in implementing health policies in Ethiopia. Ethiopia is a lower-middle-income country with limited resources to allocate to the health sector (World Bank, 2020). This situation has been compounded by the high population growth rate and the significant burden of infectious diseases such as HIV/AIDS, malaria, and tuberculosis. The lack of resources has made it difficult to provide basic healthcare services, particularly in the rural areas of the country.

Resources: A lack of necessary resources may result in incomplete policy implementation or policy failure. **Financial Resources:** Evidence shows that a lack of, or uncertainty about, financial resources is a critical challenges to policy implementation and, vice versa, successful policy implementation relies on appropriate monetary support. For example, policy implementation can be put at risk if no extra resources are made available when a new, additional policy is required to be implemented. Further challenges arise when policy implementers are unable to reallocate existing funding or to source new funding.

Human Resources and Training: A key human resource challenge is staff turnover and position instability, which can result in the loss of institutional memory and valuable experience. The lack of time that existing staff have to allocate to implementing a new or refreshed policy is frequently cited as a problem. A lack of adequate training and staff capacity building is a barrier to policy implementation.

Leadership, Commitment, and Ideology: In addition to having sufficient human resources, it is important to consider aspects of leadership, levels of commitment, and ideologies that may influence how stakeholders undertake policy implementation. Since a lack of leadership can be a challenge to implementation, existing evidence suggests identifying and supporting local and regional leaders (or “champions”) to drive implementation processes. **Infrastructure:** Infrastructure for policy implementation can include specific equipment such as IT systems or organisational structures such as partnerships. Vice versa, a lack of fit-for purpose IT systems can hamper implementation efforts.

Lack Stakeholder Engagement: Evidence suggests that relevant populations should be included in policymaking processes at legislative and regional levels to help reduce policy implementation gaps. However, it appears that brief, one-off consultation of target populations does not guarantee more effective policy implementation. It is suggested that interactions with the target population and other key stakeholders should cover the entire policy process, from the time a policy problem is identified to policy implementation. They found that a key challenge to implementing the new policy was the lack of input from frontline health-care staff to the policy development process - it was perceived that the people who developed the policy did not understand the unique challenges faced by those who would be implementing it.

Lack of Implementation Guidance and Ongoing Communication: A lack of clear guidance about implementation expectations and responsibilities for policy actions can present a significant challenge from the start of implementation. Poor communication can hamper policy implementation. There is a risk of poor

communication when, for example, policy implementation requires transmission and interpretation of nuanced ideas across different levels of governance or during integrated working among numerous organizations. **Lack of Organizational Culture:** Organizational culture is important for policy implementation because implementing agencies have significant amounts of autonomy, and are not entirely under administrative control. In addition, organisations are increasingly expected to work effectively in partnerships with other organisations that may have different values, priorities, and perspectives from their own. These factors influence how organisations will interpret and undertake policy implementation. For example, organizational resistance to change, lengthy decision-making processes, risk avoidance, and lack of coordination among service providers can be challenges to implementation.

Lack of Accountability: Accountability for enacting policy was found to be an important aspect of policy implementation quality and effectiveness. A key challenge to policy implementation is a lack of clear understanding among both policymakers and policy implementers about the distribution of responsibilities. This issue is made more complex when policies are intended to be implemented through local partnership arrangements. Accountability agreements are likely to be more effective if, within them, explicit links are drawn between government goals/mandates and actions planned for local implementation. Meanwhile, a lack of incentives encouraging compliance or a lack of sanctions for noncompliance, and voluntary uptake of a policy, may be barriers to implementation. Enforcement of accountability may overlap with the monitoring and evaluation of policy implementation. Other challenges to policy implementation can emerge when a new policy conflicts with other existing regulations and responsibilities.

Political instability: The political situation in Ethiopia has been unstable for years, resulting in significant challenges in implementing health policies. Political instability leads to frequent changes in leadership and policies, which can disrupt the continuity of health projects and programs. According to a report by the United Nations (2018), Ethiopia has experienced significant political instability, particularly in regions such as Oromia and Amhara. This instability has adversely affected the implementation of health policies and programs, especially in areas that lack adequate infrastructure and resources. **Fragmented health system:** The health system in Ethiopia is also quite fragmented, which has hindered the effective implementation of health policies. There is a lack of coordination between the various elements of the health system, particularly at the primary healthcare level. This lack of coordination has led to a duplication of efforts and the inefficient use of resources. In addition, the lack of a unified information system has made it difficult to track progress in the implementation of health policies.

Lack of the Monitoring and Evaluation: It is important to measure and analyse the progress of policy implementation in order to know to what extent it has occurred, what successes or challenges have been experienced, and to learn from these experiences. The implementation factors discussed above can be considered and incorporated into policy planning and formulation, however it will be impossible to anticipate or completely control all aspects of implementation. Therefore, a process of learning, and the capacity to continuously monitor and evaluate policy implementation, is necessary.

It concludes that challenges of the health policy implementation in Ethiopia context involves such as followed: the missed opportunities to integrate nutrition into the health sector, introduce nutrition-sensitive RMNCH interventions, and mainstream multi-sectoral nutrition programs into other sectors; along with frequent changes of national nutrition program implementing sectors officials at all levels, inadequate capacity of HEWs, and weak supply chain systems; lack of a detailed implementation plan for cascading the strategic plan into operationalization plan to align existing resources or inputs (financial, human, time and other relevant resources) with anticipated services to be delivered to clients; the challenges to organizational structures at national, regional, and sub-regional health sector in measures supporting implementation of sector-specific and multi-sectoral strategies; inadequate implementation of rational medicine use; fragmented and weak implementation of health care financing; inadequate implementation of CBHI in pastoral regions; challenges in financial utilization and liquidation at all levels; low utilization of evidence for decision making; inadequate information on social determinants and other health related activities; delayed government decision to implement social health insurance; lack of consistency in implementation of gender mainstreaming; weak law enforcements and regulatory mechanisms; appointment of public health

facility management by political affiliation, not by merit, in local governments; weak inter-sectoral collaboration; inadequately managed urbanization and industrialization; inadequate aid effectiveness and low predictability of funding.

5.2.2. Prospects of the Health Policy Implementation in the Ethiopia context

Despite the challenges, there is still hope for effective health policy implementation in Ethiopia. The following are some prospects that could help improve the situation. In an effort to understand how policy implementation occurs and how it can be improved, a great deal of research has studied this topic.

Existing research confirms that **planning for policy implementation** is best conducted during the stage of policy formulation and examination to a certain extent, the success of implementation is a function of how the original policy or legislation is developed. Existing evidence suggests that certain contexts can be more receptive to certain policies and approaches to implementation than others. Opportunities for further planning also exist during impact assessments, when the impact of policy or legislation on issues such as finances or equality are assessed. **Increased funding:** There is a need for increased funding to the health sector, particularly from domestic sources. The government has taken steps to increase health financing, but there is still a long way to go to reach the recommended 6% of the GDP. Increasing funding will enable the government to provide basic health services and improve the infrastructure and resources in the health sector. A clear message from existing evidence is that policy implementation requires a variety of resources to support the process. These include, but are not limited to **financial resources, human resources, leadership, and infrastructure**. The issue of financial resources is directly linked to the other themes in this briefing. For example, human resources, conducting consultations, maintaining infrastructure, and sustaining performance measurement and evaluation require financial support.

The availability of skilled, knowledgeable staff is important for policy implementation. Ensuring sufficient numbers of staff and the right skills require additional recruitment and training for policy implementation and managing staff turnover. Ways to retain staff may therefore need to be prioritised, for example by supporting policy implementers (including managers and service providers) by providing resources to advise and assist them with specific policy, legal, and regulatory processes. Given that staff are often trying to cope with competing priorities at local level, it is likely that direction and support must be given about how they should prioritise any new initiative. There is a consensus about the need for training to equip policy implementers, particularly at early stages of policy implementation and then in an ongoing capacity. Taken together, this suggests that different types of training may be required in policy implementation, including a) technical content to deliver policy activities, and b) training in engaging with the policy process for broader stakeholders.

These leaders can provide guidance on what policy activities are valued and can influence the general culture towards a policy topic (e.g. beliefs surrounding domestic violence). Getting sufficient levels of commitment and buy-in for policy implementation may require incentives to get staff to engage in the process. It can also be enhanced by engaging with staff and stakeholders from the beginning of policy development. It will also be important to consider the ideologies of those who will need to implement the policy. Maycraft Kall (2014) discusses the role of government and key organisations in shaping the ideology surrounding policy and legislation that it is not just the 'letter of the law' that matters, but also the 'spirit' of it, something that is signaled by the national government. For example, ideologies of practitioners who ultimately deliver a policy will influence how that policy is represented to the public who access the policy's associated services. Key Point: It is critical that the implementation process of a health policy has the infrastructure to support; the collection, synthesis, and utilisation of data; and communication and coordination within and between organisations.

Stakeholder engagement can help develop a shared understanding of policy goals and the kinds of solutions that can progress towards achieving them. In terms of best practice, the literature suggests that policymakers engage in meaningful involvement and discussions with other policy stakeholders. During this, specific

policy measures should be elaborated in detail so that the target population has an opportunity to consider them, and co-produced agreements about specific recommendations can be developed.

Identification of, and communication with, responsible parties are important tasks in policy implementation. In acknowledgement of the complexity of the policy implementation process, there is a need to balance the decisiveness of implementation guidance with flexibility given to local implementers. For example, certain specific public health interventions must be delivered by trained professionals. However, allowing local policy implementers the flexibility to decide how to make this happen and to render services appropriate for local needs, may be a facilitator to implementation. Health policy implementation can be facilitated by the development of clear guidance about expectations and the distribution of responsibilities for policy actions. This guidance will be enhanced by also building in certain flexibilities for local policy implementers to adapt to local needs. When an organization has been identified as the one responsible for implementing a health policy, it may be beneficial to develop or adjust organizational structures (e.g. working groups or steering committees), so that the health policy will be prioritized and given legitimacy within that organization.

If clear guidance exists, accountability measures and enforcement mechanisms that are well-defined and formally agreed can help ensure further clarity on roles and responsibilities, and therefore may enhance progress towards implementation goals. In addition, similarly to the section on guidance, building a certain amount of flexibility into these agreements may help policy implementers take account of learning and, as a result, adapt implementation to changing local needs. Finally, those tasked with policy implementation and held accountable for it must be provided with adequate political support and authority to undertake this work.

Strengthening the primary healthcare system is essential to achieving effective health policy implementation in Ethiopia. A strong primary healthcare system will ensure that basic healthcare services are available to all citizens, particularly those in rural areas. This could be achieved through the provision of essential medical supplies, training of healthcare workers, and the development of a unified information system. **Strengthening partnerships** is another prospect that could help improve health policy implementation in Ethiopia. Partnerships between the government, donor organizations, and the private sector could increase the resources available to the health sector. In addition, partnerships could facilitate the sharing of knowledge and expertise, leading to effective policy implementation

It advances the accountability of policymakers for health impacts through efficient, effective multi-sectoral actions; and emphasizes the need to be vigilant to prevent any unintended consequences of public policies on determinants of health, well-being, and the health system. By promoting healthy practices across all sectors, HIAP fosters inclusive, sustainable development and helps address the social determinants of health, reduce multi-sectoral risk factors, and promote health and well-being.

it conclude that prospects of the health policy implementation in the Ethiopia context along with their major activities: enhance provision of equitable and quality comprehensive health service; improve health emergency and disaster risk management; ensure community engagement and ownership; improve access to pharmaceuticals and medical devices and their rational and proper use; improve regulatory systems; improve human resource development and management; enhance informed decision-making and innovations; improve health financing; strengthen governance and leadership; improve health infrastructure; enhance digital health technology; improve traditional medicine; enhance health in all policies and strategies; enhance private engagement in the health sector; ensure integration of health in all policies and strategies.

In additions prospects of the health policy implementation includes: Positive government attention to global commitments, such as SDGs; Global PHC/UHC movement; Presence of favorable cultural and traditional self-help practices in the community; Increase in community demand for high quality of health care; Improving engagement of stakeholders (CSO and Professional associations) in improving quality of care; Increased number of health professionals' training institutions (public and private sectors) and programs; Engagement of local universities in HIS and knowledge generation; Increased number of new graduate

health workers (availability); Implementation of various reforms in the country; Presence of scientifically proven and globally accepted health technologies; Advancements in technology both globally and locally; improving internet availability, access to various media outlet and Social Networks; Enhanced community participation and engagement in health; Enhance provision of equitable and quality comprehensive health services.

5.3. Health policy analysis

Policy change in the health sector is particularly challenging because health systems are technically complex. Experience with health sector reform suggests that the costs of reform often fall on powerful and well-organized groups, while the benefits are often intended for widely dispersed and disadvantaged groups with little political influence.

5.3.1. Retrospective and prospective policy analysis

Policy analysis can be of two types, characterized as analysis of policy and analysis for policy. Analysis of policy tends to be retrospective and descriptive. It looks back at why or how a policy made its way onto the agenda, its content, and whether or not and why it has achieved its goals. Analysis for policy tends to be prospective. It is usually carried out to inform the formulation of a policy or anticipate how a policy might fare if introduced. Typically, analysis for policy will be undertaken by interested parties to assess the prospects and manage the politics of policy change in a way that meets their goals. Analysis in the early stages of policymaking, particularly in problem definition and agenda setting, are particularly important.

5.3.2. Data analysis: applying the policy triangle

Essentially, this approach conceptualizes policymaking as a process in which context, process and content, seen as three 'corners', are linked by 'actors', which may be individuals, groups or organizations, in the center of the triangle. Although this approach provides an extremely useful guide to make your exploration of health policy issues more systematic, it is more difficult to apply when you come to writing up your data because the different concepts, such as actors and processes, are so integrally intertwined. A few scholars have presented their policy analysis by talking separately about content, actors, processes and context.

The policy triangle is just one way to organize your material. Overall, it is usually easier to approach your analysis like a narrative: a story with a beginning, middle and end. In gathering your data, you may well produce a timeline: writing down the dates of a series of events, meetings or conferences, results from research studies, media stories, or a change in government, which will have informed your analysis of how the issue got on to the policy agenda. Having established how and why the issue reached the policy agenda, you can go on to describe who was involved in formulating the policy: was it largely prepared within a government department, how far did it involve others, such as the finance or social welfare ministries? At implementation you might refer to what happened once the policy was formulated – how was it executed? Was there good communication between policymakers and those putting it into practice?

The policy triangle framework was initially developed for health policy analysis by Walt and Gilson (1994). Since then it has been applied to other areas of public policy, such as agriculture and education. The policy triangle consists of context, process and content with actors at the center of the framework (Figure 1).

The policy triangle depicted in Figure 1 has summarized the policy actors and context of the health extension policy development in Ethiopia.

Figure 1: Policy triangle of Health Extension Program in Ethiopia.

A. Actors

An actor can be an individual, a group, an organization or the government. Individuals have their own values and expectations. Groups are usually interest based. They do not want to assume a political office, and would rather influence decision makers. For example, an association of diabetes patients in Ethiopia may lobby for increased health care expenditure on diabetes care and treatment. Organizations include non-governmental, not-for-profit and private for-profit. For-profit organizations may want to advance policies that maximise their profit. For example, pharmaceutical companies may push for increased expenditure on treatment because ultimately they sell drugs and medical devices. Alternatively, consider MIDROC Ethiopia that employs thousands of individuals and may draft a policy for the provision of free treatment for HIV patients working for the company hoping that productivity will rise. The state is also an important actor in the policy process. Local, state and federal state officials wield power in formulating and legislating policy. However, the actors are not independent. The power of individuals depends on their position in the organization, which in turn affects their access to knowledge, resources and authority within or outside their organization. The power of organizations in turn depends on the values and beliefs of the individuals who operate with that organization and who shape its culture.

Example 2

Think about the social health insurance policy in Ethiopia. List the actors that are involved with the policy. Does a way of grouping them suggest itself to you?

Solution

You may have listed the following actors and grouped them as follows:

- government (ministry of health, ministry of labour and social affairs, the parliament, the council of ministers)
- NGOs (USAID)
- interest groups (labour unions)
- individuals (academics working on health systems, health policy, health services management).

B. Context

Context refers to political, economic and social systemic factors that affect policy, process and content. Leicher (1979) suggests four types of factor.

Situational factors: these are transient, non-permanent events. They might be short-term, like famine, war or election of a new party to a public office. Or they may occur for a sustained period, as in the recognition

of an HIV epidemic. They are strong in making the public focus on a particular issue and may lead to a policy change.

Structural factors: these depend on the political system in which the policymaking takes place. Such factors are more permanent than situational ones. The rule by which power is acquired and the existence of (or lack of) free media affect how policy is framed. Free media bring issues to the attention of the public and popularise them. Uganda has successfully used mass media campaigns promoting sexual abstinence, monogamy and condom use in order to reduce the incidence of HIV infection (Singh, *et.al*, 2003).

Economic factors are also structural. A country with a small gross domestic product (GDP) may find it difficult ensuring universal health care. A mandatory health insurance policy would not occur when a large proportion of people of working age are unemployed or underemployed. GDP growth may present an opportunity to subsidise costly health policies. For example, Rwanda has harnessed the benefits of fast economic growth to introduce universal health care policy. But there is a challenge here. Other structural factors including demography for example, age structure of the population – affect the cost of health care. In a country with an aging population, the GDP growth may not match the increasing need for health care of the elderly. Ethiopia has successfully enacted and is implementing policies on child health as well as on sexual and reproductive health because the country's population is young.

Cultural context: The third factor that builds context is cultural – a domain term for the history, language, customs, norms and religion that make up a society. Cultural norms in most parts of Ethiopia that dictate women as subservient to the wishes of men have hampered the utilisation of modern contraceptives in that country. Husband disapproval is often cited as the major reason for low contraceptive coverage rate in Ethiopia. In the early 21st century, religious beliefs have contributed to the resistance to the increased use of condoms for the prevention of HIV.

International factor: The fourth factor that affects policy process is international or exogenous. Government aid agencies, such as USAID, wield a tremendous influence on how policy is framed and the agenda set. The President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief, largely operating through USAID in Ethiopia, has been instrumental in injecting nearly 1 billion US dollars into the Ethiopian health care system to scale up antiretroviral treatment to about a quarter of a million people living with HIV/AIDS. It has also funded care and support to about 1.1 million HIV-positive individuals (US Government, 2014).

Example 3

Think about the social health insurance policy in Ethiopia and discuss the contextual factors that influenced its enactment.

Solution

Some of the contextual factors affecting the social health insurance policy that you might have identified are:

- ✓ situational – increased awareness of the mixed disease burden with the rise of chronic diseases requiring sustained treatment and care
- ✓ political – increased government commitment to the health of the population
- ✓ economic – increased GDP growth of Ethiopia
- ✓ cultural – increased demand for modern health care partly due to the shift away from traditional medicine
- ✓ international – USAID assistance both technical and financial.

C. Process

The policy process is about the stages of policymaking described in the stages heuristic including policy formulation, adoption and implementation. There are sub-processes in each stage and they are not all equally important.

For example, in a policy process analysis framework developed for UNICEF to analyse the implementation of the removal of user fees in six sub-Saharan African countries some sub-processes have been found to be more important than others (Hercot *et al*, 2011).

Out of the 20 hypotheses we developed, some are less supported by the literature, like the sequencing of the implementation in phases. Other hypotheses are supported by most authors, like the involvement of key implementation stakeholders in the formulation stage, the need for broad communication strategies and the importance of monitoring the reform. Still other hypotheses could be reformulated. For example, the distinction between the two hypotheses on international and national evidence could be merged in one more comprehensive hypothesis. Another example is the relevance of separating ‘the process of planning implementation steps’ and ‘the need to sequence the reform’ in two distinct hypotheses. Obviously, the latter could be seen as a part of the former. Although these discussions are valid and should take place each time the framework is used, we suggest that delineating a (sub-) practice helps to draw attention to this practice.

D. Content

The content of the policy can be as broad as the Ethiopian Growth and Transformation Plan (GTP) and as narrow as the HIV/AIDS policy. The GTP, for example, outlines targets to be achieved by the plan and its content is very broad in that it contains issues of agriculture, trade, education and health among others, with objective, indicator and implementation agency for each issue. In contrast, HIV/AIDS policy deals with specific issues around the disease, such as prevention, treatment and care. The responsibility for implementing the GTP is shared between different government ministries while for HIV/AIDS the sole responsibility lies with the ministry of health.

A number of policy options can be under discussion for a specific problem, and often the options are vaguely defined during formation. Implementation usually refines the options. Decision on which option to pursue is largely dependent on political discourse and power.

Since the policy triangle framework emphasises the power of the different actors, we will comment on power. Power is the ability to influence others. One may influence others by coercion or by manipulation, but legitimate power avoids both of these. Manipulation is a persuasive method of controlling the thought of others. For example, propaganda can be a tool of manipulation. Monetary incentive, or lack thereof, can also be considered as a manipulative tool.

The policy development process of HEP in Ethiopia satisfies both Kingdon 2014 and Hall et al 1975 models. The Kingdon model is satisfied as described in Figure 3. As per the Hall et al. model, access to primary healthcare is a legitimate concern fully recognized by the government’s HSDP I performance evaluation. HEP is also accepted as a feasible program to address the issue with a limited resource and less intensive 1-year training of HEWs with basic health service education as compared with more intensive training of doctors and allied health workforce for curative services. The HEP had wider public support and the community was a part of the program to partly cover the expenditures for constructing health posts and providing residence for HEWs.

Figure 2: Policy development of HEP in Ethiopia from Kingdon model perspective.

5.3.3. Studying how policies are formed and implemented health policy analysis

A **case study** is an important study design that helps us to answer questions on how policies are formed and implemented.

Gilson (2012) notes that a case study is a study of a phenomenon in a real-life context using multiple sources of data. Yin (2009) argues that the case study approach is mainly valuable in a situation when there is no clear boundary between the phenomenon and the context. A case can be an event, organization, community, process (policy formation or policy implementation), relationship between stakeholders, policy intervention or subgroup in a policy.

Gilson (2012) suggests that case studies are important for health policy analysis for three reasons.

Firstly, health policy cannot be separated from the context in which it takes place. For example, suppose the policy intervention is health promotion targeted at women of reproductive age to encourage them to give birth in a health facility. What affects how these women respond to the policy intervention? Some of the factors that influence whether a woman will avail herself of the health intervention relate to her personal circumstance such as her age and her education. Other factors are more contextual such as the economic status of her household, and the values and beliefs of the community in which the intervention is taking place. These beliefs may dictate that a woman's role is to stay at home to raise children and to cook food for the family which gives them very little leeway on whether to take the intervention or not. All these contextual factors may operate independently or may interact to influence how the intervention is taken up by the target group.

There are also contextual factors related to the provider of the intervention: consider opening hours, the service package, the availability of services and cost of services. The mothers may be able to access the service only during certain hours of the day which could result in an underutilization of the intervention.

Case studies are an important study design available to policy analysts helping them to unearth both beneficiary and provider related contextual factors.

Secondly, the same policy intervention is often perceived differently by different actors. Case studies help to describe the perception of actors towards the intervention activities, thereby contributing to a better implementation. Thirdly, actors interact in a unique way. Therefore, there is a need to study how the actors relate to each other and how they interact to shape a policy change.

Three types of case study designs are described by Gilson (2012). Single case study design occurs when a researcher identifies one case and studies it in detail. For example, the study of social health insurance formation process in Ethiopia. A multiple cases study design, in contrast, involves one issue being studied in multiple settings. Its purpose is comparison. The following text is an abstract on the study of HIV/ AIDS policy – condom promotion or lack thereof – in Botswana and Uganda. Note that it uses the multiple cases method. It highlights the differences between the two countries in leadership, engagement of religious groups and ‘procedures of social compliance’.

A comparison of HIV/AIDS policies in Botswana and Uganda is revealing. It helps to highlight the kinds of policies that are necessary to come to terms with the pandemic in Africa, where it is already a public health disaster. It is argued that the promotion of condoms at an early stage proved to be counter-productive in Botswana, whereas the lack of condom promotion during the 1980s and early 1990s contributed to the relative success of behavior change strategies in Uganda. Other important factors included national and local level leadership, the engagement (or alienation) of religious groups and local healers and, most controversially, procedures of social compliance. We end with a call for more draconian measures than are currently envisaged. (Allen, 2004). The third and most complex type of case study is nested case, a situation when one case is embedded in another or encompasses others. For example, a case study aimed at describing how social health insurance policy is implemented in Jimma Zone can be embedded in a case study on how that policy is being implemented in the Oromia administrative region.

Elements of process evaluation: Process evaluation should include as a minimum the content, context and actors of implementation. We need to ask what activities are being implemented and in what context they are implemented. The political, economic and social contexts are important. A policy intervention might be taking place in a decentralized health system, for example that of Ethiopia. The perception of the woreda health department and its power to incorporate or modify the elements of the intervention affect the implementation process. The department may or may not have adequate resources. The regional health bureau may need to assign additional health professionals to a specific woreda. In process evaluation, we need to study whether there is an adequate budget to finance the additional personnel. In addition, does the setting allow their optimal functioning? Another important element of the context is social factors, which may encompass the ethnic composition of the implementation area. Furthermore, we need to describe the perception of the target population towards the intervention. Actors are inalienable parts of the implementation. The actors may range from the local official to international partners. In between are the health professionals, the community, interest groups and influential leaders in the community. Thus, the values and expectations of the different actors and the interaction among them are crucial in determining the success or failure of any activity.

6. Conclusion

The implementation of a policy is an integral part of the policy process. “Policy implementation is what develops between the establishment of an apparent intention on the part of government to do something, or to stop something, and the ultimate impact in the world of action.” Introduces the basic concepts of health policy, plans and programs. It also discussed the framework of health policy, plan and program implementation and analysis.

It is well known that there are a number of challenges when implementing national health policies. The challenges of health policy implementation in Ethiopia are significant. Political instability, inadequate infrastructure and resources, inadequate funding, and a fragmented health system, a lack planning for policy implementation, a key human resource challenge, a lack of adequate training and staff capacity building, a

lack of leadership, commitment, and ideology, lack stakeholder engagement, lack of implementation guidance and ongoing communication, lack of organizational culture, lack of accountability, lack of the monitoring and evaluation; along with frequent changes of National Nutrition Program implementing sectors officials at all levels, inadequate capacity of HEWs, and weak supply chain systems; inadequate implementation of CBHI in pastoral regions; low utilization of evidence for decision making; inadequate information on social determinants and other health related activities; lack of consistency in implementation of gender mainstreaming; weak inter-sectoral collaboration; Inadequately managed urbanization and industrialization are among the major challenges.

However, there are prospects for improvement of the health policy implementation in Ethiopia context, such as increased funding, strengthening of the primary healthcare system, and strengthening of partnerships. enhance provision of equitable and quality comprehensive health service; improve health emergency and disaster risk management; ensure community engagement and ownership; improve human resource development and management; enhance informed decision-making and innovations; improve health financing; strengthen governance and leadership; improve health infrastructure; enhance digital health technology; improve traditional medicine; improving engagement of stakeholders in improving quality of care; increased number of health professionals' training institutions (public and private sectors) and programs; engagement of local universities in his and knowledge generation; advancements in technology both globally and locally; improving internet availability, access to various media outlet and social networks; enhanced community participation and engagement in health; enhance provision of equitable and quality comprehensive health services; enhance private engagement in the health sector; ensure integration of health in all policies and strategies. Effective health policy implementation is essential to achieving improved health outcomes in Ethiopia. The unit also addresses the links between policy, context, actors and process. Policy development, policy implementation and policy analysis are interrelated steps. In addition, it is clear that policy analysis is important for future policy development.

7. Recommendation

It recommended that effective health policy implementation is critical and essential to achieving success of health policies outcome in Ethiopia. National, regional and local levels require efforts will also be make to integrate and mainstream elements of the health policy within the policies and programs of all other sectors, fostering inter-sectoral collaboration. In require effort to understand how policy implementation occurs and how it can be improved provides suggestions for policy decision-makers at national and local levels to close the implementation gap. Developing a policy is just the first step; for policies to contribute to the successful delivery of health services, they must be effectively implemented.

- ❖ Health policy implementation must be adequately and sustainably financed; the availability of skilled, knowledgeable staff who are offered ongoing training is important for health policy implementation.
- ❖ Health policy implementation requires commitment from people in leadership positions, buy-in from all relevant stakeholders, and consideration of the values and ideologies of those who will implement the policy.
- ❖ It is critical that the implementation process of a health policy has the infrastructure to support: (a) the collection, synthesis, and utilization of data; and (b) communication and coordination within and between organizations.
- ❖ Meaningful involvement of relevant stakeholders and target populations in the entire policy process can help reduce policy implementation challenges.
- ❖ Health policy implementation can be facilitated by the development of clear guidance about expectations and the distribution of responsibilities for policy actions. This guidance will be enhanced by also building in certain flexibilities for local policy implementers to adapt to local needs.
- ❖ Planning for health policy implementation can be improved by considering the organizational culture(s) of the organization(s) who will be involved in the implementation process.

- ❖ Accountability mechanisms surrounding a policy's implementation can be improved by: (a) co-producing (with relevant policy stakeholders) clear agreements about responsibilities for implementation activities; and (b) aligning responsibilities for the new policy with existing responsibilities.
- ❖ Monitoring and evaluating a health policy's implementation is a critical, ongoing process, which is necessary to measure progress and provide important learning for improvement.
- ❖ Policy implementation cannot be entirely controlled, so it is important to engage in continuous monitoring and evaluation throughout the policy implementation lifespan.
- ❖ Develop and implement legal framework and implementation arrangement for effective implementation of multi-sectoral actions.
- ❖ Provide feedback on implementation by; Collecting evidence on problems as they arise; Bridging gaps between policy makers and service users by facilitating links and feedback

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